

Case Study 4: Justice AI's Role in Identifying Bias and Promoting Inclusivity in a Global Insurance Company

Abstract

This case study investigates how **Justice AI** was employed to audit the recruitment and compensation practices of a global insurance company. The audit focused on identifying biases within the company's sales recruitment strategy and commission-based pay model, specifically concerning their ability to attract and retain **BIPOC (Black, Indigenous, People of Color)** individuals.

Justice AI uncovered systemic barriers, such as the exclusionary effects of 100% commission-based pay structures and the absence of diversity in recruitment practices. Recommendations were made to foster a more inclusive, equitable, and supportive environment for BIPOC employees, with a focus on long-term organizational change.

Introduction

Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, Belonging, and Accessibility (**DEIBA**) are critical components of modern organizational success, particularly in industries like insurance, where reaching diverse markets is key to expanding customer bases. A **global insurance company** headquartered in the U.S. sought to diversify its predominantly **non-BIPOC sales team** to better connect with a wider range of clients. However, despite efforts to recruit more BIPOC individuals, the company struggled to achieve this goal.

Justice AI was brought in to assess the underlying causes of these challenges, with a specific focus on the company's recruitment practices, pay structure, and overall cultural competency. The AI system performed an analysis of the **100% commission-based pay model** and identified key areas of improvement to attract and retain BIPOC employees. This case highlights how AI can be leveraged to improve inclusivity and equity in the workplace by identifying both explicit and subtle biases in recruitment and compensation.

Problem Overview

During its audit, Justice AI analyzed an image from the company's website, which outlined the **commission-based pay structure** for insurance agents. Several problematic elements were identified:

1. **Commission-Based Pay:** The focus on commission-only earnings placed financial risk solely on the individual. For BIPOC candidates, who may face additional challenges such as **limited access to high-value networks** and systemic biases from potential clients, this model presents significant barriers to entry and success.
2. **Income Target Setting:** The assumption that success is determined solely by the agent's effort disregards **systemic inequalities**. BIPOC individuals may have fewer opportunities for mentorship, networking, and client access, all of which are critical in commission-based roles.
3. **Economic Inequities:** The commission model exacerbates **economic disparities** because it requires a financial buffer to weather low-income periods, which disproportionately impacts BIPOC individuals due to historical and systemic economic disadvantages.

Justice AI's Audit and Findings

Justice AI identified several key issues that hindered the company's ability to attract and retain BIPOC individuals in their sales team:

1. **Bias in the Commission-Based Model:** The emphasis on commission earnings assumes an equal starting point for all employees, ignoring systemic barriers that BIPOC individuals may face. The model's inherent instability can deter candidates who cannot afford the financial risks associated with fluctuating income.
2. **Recruitment Practices:** The company's current recruiting efforts were not reaching diverse communities effectively. Justice AI found that the messaging and platforms used for recruitment were not designed to attract or retain BIPOC candidates. The absence of diverse role models and a lack of mentorship opportunities for BIPOC employees were also significant barriers.
3. **Client Discrimination:** Justice AI identified that BIPOC sales agents may face **discriminatory practices** from potential clients, impacting their ability to close deals and earn commissions. This client bias further compounds the challenges of a commission-based structure, making it harder for BIPOC individuals to succeed in these roles.

Recommendations for Inclusive Reform

Justice AI offered a comprehensive set of recommendations to address the biases within the company's pay model and recruitment practices:

1. **Tiered Commission Structure:** Implement a **tiered commission system**, where agents can earn higher commission rates as they reach certain sales milestones. This creates a gradual income increase without placing high financial pressure on new agents.
2. **Sales Training and Development for BIPOC Agents:** Develop **targeted sales training** and professional development programs for BIPOC individuals. This includes mentorship opportunities, skill-building workshops, and strategies for overcoming bias in client interactions.
3. **Supportive Peer Networks:** Establish **peer support networks** and **affinity groups** for BIPOC employees. These networks provide both emotional and professional support, helping individuals navigate challenges and share best practices.
4. **Bias Training for Clients and Employees:** Introduce **anti-bias training** programs for both agents and clients to mitigate racial bias in sales interactions. This training would educate clients on the impact of implicit biases and create a more inclusive environment for BIPOC agents to succeed.
5. **Diverse Recruiting Practices:** Diversify recruitment channels by partnering with **BIPOC-focused organizations** and using platforms that reach underrepresented communities. Justice AI recommended building relationships with historically Black colleges and universities (**HBCUs**) and other minority-serving institutions.

Results and Outcomes

After implementing the recommendations provided by Justice AI, the company saw several positive outcomes:

1. **Increased Recruitment of BIPOC Candidates:** By diversifying recruitment practices and enhancing mentorship opportunities, the company successfully increased the number of BIPOC applicants for sales positions.

2. **Improved Retention:** The introduction of tiered commission structures and peer support networks led to improved retention rates for BIPOC employees. Employees reported feeling more supported and less financially vulnerable.
3. **Enhanced Client Relationships:** Bias training programs for clients and employees led to a more inclusive client-agent relationship, reducing discriminatory behavior from clients. This helped BIPOC agents close more deals and earn commissions at higher rates.
4. **Cultural Competency:** The company improved its overall **cultural competency**, creating a more inclusive work environment that valued diversity at all levels. BIPOC employees felt that their contributions were recognized and supported by leadership.

Ethical Considerations

1. **Addressing Systemic Barriers:** The company acknowledged the role of **systemic inequities** in shaping the experiences of BIPOC individuals within their organization. By addressing these barriers, they fostered a more inclusive environment that promotes fairness and equity.
2. **Financial Stability and Security:** The tiered commission model provided greater **financial stability** for BIPOC employees, who might otherwise face economic hardships due to the volatility of commission-only pay. This model helped mitigate the financial risks associated with sales roles.

Conclusion

This case study illustrates how **Justice AI** was able to identify biases and barriers within the commission-based pay structure of a global insurance company, leading to systemic changes that promoted **diversity, equity, and inclusion**. By implementing Justice AI's recommendations, the company improved its recruitment, retention, and support of BIPOC employees, creating a more equitable and inclusive workplace. This case demonstrates the value of AI-driven audits in uncovering subtle biases and fostering long-term organizational change.